

FEATURES OF THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF YUCCA IN AGRO- ECOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT OF THE IMERETI REGION

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Annotation. *Yuccas belong to a group of very useful plants due to their multipurpose use. This plant was introduced into our country in the second half of the 19th century and is quite widely distributed, but complete scientific research on the introduction of this plant into culture in western Georgian conditions has not been conducted. The study of yucca bioecology in Imereti's agroecological environment is also interesting because it is, by its phylogeny, a plant of dry climate, semi-desert, and desert, and studying its biology in our conditions against the backdrop of quite abundant precipitation gives us very interesting material.*

It is assumed that against the background of global climate changes, technical crops may occupy a very relevant place alongside other crops in western Georgia's farming, and among them one of the important directions is the cultivation of medicinal plants.

Biochemical studies of some yucca species have revealed that their leaves (mostly the old leaves) contain tigogenin and steroidal saponin. The latter is a source for the synthesis of steroidal hormonal preparations.

Observations on the growth and development of yucca species were carried out in the Kutaisi Botanical Garden, where several species of the genus Yucca are introduced. Observations were conducted on both adult specimens, and the biological features of young seedling growth and development were also studied. One of the important issues when cultivating a new crop is the study of soil-climatic conditions of the zone where we plan to introduce the crop. It was precisely with consideration of the influence of these factors that the study of yucca crop growth and development was conducted in the Imereti's agroecological environment.

Keywords: *Yucca; cultivation; medicinal plant; bio-ecology; soils; introduction.*

At the current stage, as a result of global warming, there are such drastic changes in climate that introduce certain serious adjustments to the production of ancient and tested cultures of farming, making it necessary to replace them with new ones.

In Georgia, and particularly in western Georgia, it is expected that in the near future, industrial crops may occupy a more relevant place in farming. For the diversity of crops, we believe that among industrial crops, one of the most important are medicinal plants, which represent a very interesting and promising direction. When the crop is not widespread in farming, the range of issues to be studied about this culture is very large. It is necessary to study the growth and development indicators of individual varieties of crops, their agrobiological and economic characteristics, their technical indicators and chemical composition, as well as to study how resistant these crops are to pests and diseases, and so on.

One of the important issues when introducing new crops is the study of soil-climatic conditions of the zone where we plan to cultivate them. The issues discussed below relate to the relationship and requirements for soil conditions.

Imereti is a mountainous region. Its soils are characterized by great diversity according to their genesis and agro-productive indicators. As in all mountainous countries, the formation of soil cover in Imereti is subject to the principle of vertical zonation. Here, according to natural historical peculiarities, through the combined influence of climate, relief, bioclimate, geological structures,

human impact, and other factors, over the centuries, very interesting and different types of soils have been formed.

The soil cover in the Imereti region has been formed as follows:

1. Meadow alluvial soils
2. Yellow earth-brown loamy soils
3. Yellow earth-brown soils
4. Yellow earth soils
5. Red earth soils
6. Humus-carbonate soils
7. Ash-grey soils
8. Mountain-meadow subalpine soils

The research related to such diversity of soil cover and generally the issue of adaptation to climatic conditions concerns the peculiarities of yucca growth and development in Imereti's agroecological environment.

Yuccas belong to a group of very useful plants due to their multipurpose use. This plant was introduced into our country in the second half of the 19th century and is quite widely distributed, but complete scientific research on the introduction of this plant into culture in western Georgian conditions has not been conducted.

The study of yucca bioecology in Imereti's agroecological environment is also interesting because it is, by its phylogeny, a plant of dry climate, semi-desert, and desert, and studying its biology in our conditions against the backdrop of quite abundant precipitation gives us very interesting material.

Yuccas are among the introduced plants. Their homeland is the southern part of North America and Central America.

Yucca is a fiber plant. Yucca leaves contain fiber, and their fibers are strong and have a silk-like shine; they simultaneously remind us of linen and silk fiber. From yucca fiber we can obtain packaging material, rope (twine), and cord. It can also be used to make coarse fabrics, bags, tarpaulins, marine ropes, and linen-like fabric, which after processing acquires a silky shine. Yucca leaves are often used as covering material, especially in viticulture. The fiber yield from yucca leaves is quite high. It has been determined that from 1 hectare of yucca plantation, 25 centners of yucca leaves can be produced, from which the fiber yield reaches 5 centners.

Biochemical studies of some yucca species have revealed that their leaves (mostly the old leaves) contain tigogenin and steroidal saponin. The latter is a source for the synthesis of steroidal hormonal preparations.

Thus, yucca is used in medicine as raw material for obtaining various medicinal preparations. The first experiments in this direction were yucca culture plantations grown in eastern Georgia, in dry climatic conditions, which supplied raw materials to the pharmaco-chemical industry. Similar plantations can also be grown in western Georgia.

Yucca is a honey plant, and some yuccas can also make marketable honey. Although yucca flower honey yield is not large, it deserves attention in other ways. Yucca blooms from early spring to late autumn, and it is not characterized by any regularity in the flowering period, which enables bees to take nectar from yucca flowers even during periods when other honey plants are not blooming, thereby reducing bee downtime. Thus, yucca is a very useful plant due to its multipurpose use.

Fig. 1 Glorious Yucca

From a medicinal perspective, *Yucca gloriosa* L. (glorious, beautiful yucca) is particularly distinguished.

This plant is characterized by a short, often branched, thick stem that ends with a densely arranged rosette of leaves spread in a fan-like form. Adult specimens of glorious yucca reach up to 5 meters in height. The leaves are erect, leathery, and dark green in color, with leaf edges decorated with yellowish-brown edging. Young leaves are sometimes serrated, while older leaves rarely show small threads.

Leaf length is 50-60 cm, width 4-5 cm. The leaf gradually narrows at the base while being widest at 2/3 of its length from the base. It narrows again toward the tip and ends with a sharp, strong spine.

The inflorescence is paniculate, 1-1.5 m high. It bears 200-250 flowers. The flowers are large, and bell-shaped and do not open completely. They are arranged drooping on the flower spike. The flower coloration is cream-white. Often the corolla petals are covered with reddish-purple spots on the outer side at the base.

The fruit is a fleshy box with 6 chambers of elongated, egg-like form. The length is 5-6 cm. It blooms several times a year.

Yucca is quite frost-resistant. It is not damaged even at -20°C , and is also less demanding on the moisture. It is a highly wind-resistant plant, which is an essential factor during wind erosion. It grows on all types of soil, including excessively moist, swampy alkaline soils. However, in the latter case, its development is sharply retarded.

It reproduces by seeds and vegetatively. It is of incomparable beauty during flowering, as 3-4 inflorescences bloom simultaneously on one plant, which gives the plant exceptional beauty.

The homeland of glorious yucca is the southern states of North America (Atlantic Ocean coasts), from North Carolina to Florida and the eastern shores of the Gulf of Mexico.

In some Central American countries, its medicinal properties are recognized by both traditional and alternative medicine. There, the leaves of glorious yucca represent both industrial raw material and are used for the production of steroidal saponins, which are used for hormone synthesis.

In folk medicine, *Yucca gloriosa* L. extract is used to treat arthritis; it has strengthening, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, and bactericidal therapeutic effects.

The leaves of glorious yucca contain large amounts of saponin - steroidal saponins and aglycones. Additionally, it contains steroidal saponin-tigogenin, as well as antioxidants, enzymes, and mucilage. Yucca flower extract contains selenium and zinc, as well as steroidal saponins and sugar.

The medicinal properties of yucca genus plants, as well as their chemical composition, have not been fully studied. Scientists have not conducted research that would confirm or deny the plant's healing power. However, it is assumed that due to the large amount of saponins and steroidal saponin-tigogenin contained in *Yucca gloriosa*, it may have anti-inflammatory effects. This allows the plant to act as a hormonal corticosteroid agent and cope with rheumatoid arthritis. The medicinal properties of glorious yucca also aim to eliminate skin itching during allergies, strengthen immunity, improve metabolism, and renew cells in the human body.

The spectrum of beneficial effects of glorious yucca is very diverse. It is used to treat headaches, arthritis, low blood pressure, intestinal polyps, prostate, and meteorism. In folk medicine, yucca is used to treat skin diseases such as neurodermatitis, psoriasis, and eczema. Yucca leaf juice is used during viral rashes.

According to literature, yucca contains antioxidants, chlorophyll, enzymes, and other beneficial substances. Medications prepared from yucca raw materials reduce cholesterol, increase the body's resistance to various diseases, and help remove polyps in the intestines.

Yucca has a beneficial effect on the respiratory system, helps cleanse the body of harmful substances, and increases arterial pressure.

The plant's large, fleshy leaves contain steroidal saponins; yucca root is widely used (especially in the USA) to treat arthritis. A positive effect is achieved due to the plant's anti-inflammatory properties.

The root contains toxic glycosides, so it is impossible to use the root without preliminary processing. Processing includes soaking, steeping, and boiling.

The leaves have medicinal value. Leaves are collected before flowering, cleaned of impurities, and then dried in the sun, spreading them in thin layers. They are stored in well-ventilated places. The storage period for raw materials is 5 years.

Given that *Yucca gloriosa* has not been sufficiently studied, it should be used medicinally with caution and on the recommendation of an experienced doctor. The use of glorious yucca is not recommended for pregnant women, during lactation, and for children.

We conduct observations for yucca cultivation at the Kutaisi Botanical Garden.

The Kutaisi Botanical Garden has several species of yucca. It is found both in the park among plantings and in groups for decorating individual corners. The total number of plantings exceeds 200.

Glorious yucca (*Yucca gloriosa*) is one of the most widespread species. It is very often found in private farms and is used both decoratively and for other purposes. In the Kutaisi Botanical Garden, it is represented by several dozen specimens. It is found both in groups and as solitaires. It is characterized by beautiful flowering. It blooms regularly, often twice during the season. It does not develop fruit. It is distinguished by great endurance and is relatively more resistant to unfavorable environmental conditions. Wind cannot harm glorious yucca; it loves sunny places, but in the garden it is also found in shaded places, though they are relatively less developed.

Observation of yucca growth and development was conducted in two stages. Both the vegetative activity of adult plants and the growth and development of young seedlings, that is, the biological features of the juvenile period, were studied.

From adult plants, 3 species and one form were selected as observation objects: *Yucca aloifolia* L.; *Y.a.f. marginata*; *Yucca filamentosa* L.; *Yucca gloriosa* L. The introduction of these species into the Kutaisi Botanical Garden occurred relatively early, and visual observation of them gives us a complete picture of the peculiarities of yucca vegetation throughout the season. Observations were conducted on the following indicators: the beginning and end of vegetation were determined, and the

duration of the vegetative period. The dynamics of leaf and rosette growth during the vegetative period were recorded, and yucca leaf growth periods were determined by months. The regularity between yucca's vegetative and generative activities was established. Observation data on yucca growth and development are presented in tables.

Many factors influence the beginning of vegetation. The most important of these factors is the average daily air temperature. For subtropical plants, the optimal temperature for the beginning of vegetation is 10-15°C. However, exposure and orographic conditions are noteworthy and should be considered. On southern exposure, vegetation begins several days earlier than in specimens presented on northern exposure. It should be noted that the earliest growth was observed in 2020.

If we compare the species themselves, it turns out that the difference in vegetation start time between species is insignificant and averages 5-6 days. *Yucca aloifolia* begins vegetation relatively early, while *Yucca filamentosa* starts latest. Such an insignificant difference is explained not by the characteristic biological features of the species but by the plant's life form.

Fig. 2 Yucca seedling

Yucca aloifolia is a standard plant, located 2-3 m above ground level, while *Yucca filamentosa* is almost spread on the ground surface, where much lower temperatures are observed than 1-2 m above ground level. This temperature difference is quite sufficient for plants to differ from each other at the beginning of vegetation.

The first table presents the results of observations on yucca vegetation dynamics during 2020-2022.

As shown in the table, the end of vegetation for almost all species and in all years of observation was noted in late October or the first half of November. It should be explained that when we speak of the end of vegetation, we have in mind the vegetative activity of the plant, its growth, while regarding generation, that is, flowering, this process sometimes continues late, and flowering is noted even in January itself. From this we can conclude that the cessation of yucca vegetation and growth stoppage are forced, which confirms that this plant is of tropical origin and can begin active vegetative activity at any time of the year as soon as favorable environmental conditions arise. For different yucca species, the length of the vegetation period is 229-239 days, which averages 8 months. The difference in vegetation period length is very insignificant and is almost equal for all species.

According to this data, we can conclude that yucca vegetation begins in the second half of February and early March. It ends in late October or the first half of November. The difference between these species is insignificant.

Table 1

Dynamics of Yucca Vegetation by Years

Years	2020			2021			2022			Average		
	Vegetation		Duration of vegetation period (days)	Vegetation		Duration of vegetation period (days)	Vegetation		Duration of vegetation period (days)	Vegetation		Duration of vegetation period (days)
	Beginning	End		Beginning	End		Beginning	End		Beginning	End	
Yucca aloifolia	21.02	10.11	257	05.02	22.10	228	03.03	20.10	231	19.02	28.10	238
Y.a. f. marginata	02.03	27.10	239	05.02	15.10	221	10.03	20.10	224	24.02	21.10	228
Yucca filamentosa	07.03	27.10	232	20.02	20.10	211	10.03	20.11	255	03.03	21.10	232
Yucca gloriosa	10.03	05.11	239	20.02	24.10	215	10.03	15.11	250	04.03	04.11	234

The annual growth of yucca is represented by a rosette. The differentiation and formation of the rosette occur at the base of the previous year's flower stem. If the plant did not flower in the previous year, then the rosette growth represents a continuation of the previous year's growth, and in this case the rosette growth begins at a relatively early stage.

Table 2

Leaf Differentiation Depending on the Growth

Species	Total number of leaves	From these					
		Rudimentary		Normal		Incomplete	
		Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%
Y.gloriosa	42	10	23,8	22	52,4	9	21,4
Y.aloifolia	51	12	23,5	26	51,0	7	13,7
Y.a.f.marginata	52	13	25,0	24	46,2	14	27,0
Y.filamentosa	34	4	11,8	23	67,6	6	17,6

It should be noted that leaves formed at different times during the vegetation period differ morphologically strongly from each other. The difference is mainly noticeable in the size of the leaves, and as a result of their differentiation, 3 forms of leaves emerged: normal leaf, underdeveloped leaf, and rudimentary leaf. We consider rudimentary leaves to be undeveloped leaves that formed earliest on plants with renewed vegetation. It stops growing prematurely and remains on the plant. Normal leaves are those that have reached their full development, while incomplete leaves are still growing leaves. Table 12 presents the percentage indicators of the differentiation process of leaves formed during the vegetation period.

For a complete characterization of yucca vegetation and general development, we studied individual specimens of yuccas introduced in the botanical garden and determined some of their biometric indicators, the data of which are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Some Biometric Indicators of Adult Yucca

Species	Plant age	Stem		Number of leaves on the plant (pcs)	Leaf	
		Height (m)	Diameter (cm)		Average area, cm ²	Average length, cm
<i>Y. gloriosa</i>	24	27	37	496	163	67
<i>Y. aloifolia</i>	Undeterminate	6.8	44	324	127	42
<i>Y. a. f. marginata</i>	11	1,6	12	337	119	44
<i>Y. filamentosa</i>	13	0,5	6	285	103	57

Thus, different yucca species, regardless of the number of leaves, have assimilative surfaces of different sizes. Among the studied species, *Yucca gloriosa* has the largest total leaf area, while *Yucca filamentosa* has the smallest one. The remaining species occupy intermediate positions.

The flowering and fruiting of yuccas differ sharply from other plants. The course of their flower phenophases is affected by a complex of environmental factors, which makes the dynamics of phenophases unstable.

Observations of yucca flowering and fruiting were conducted visually throughout the entire vegetation period. The same specimens were selected for observation from all species that flowered in the botanical garden. These plants are *Y. aloifolia*, *Y. gloriosa*, *Y. a. f. marginata*, and *Y. filamentosa*.

The course, duration, and character of flowering phenological phases were described, as well as their relationship with environmental conditions. The biological features of pollination and flower fertilization were studied.

For yucca flowering, so-called “readiness” is required, which is expressed by a whole series of physiological and biochemical processes that occur in the plant before flowering. Only after passing through the complete phase of vegetative activity does the differentiation of flowering organs and flowering occur. During the flowering period, the plant's vegetative growth ceases.

Yuccas are often characterized by flowering twice in one vegetation period. During observation and recording, yucca flowering was conditionally divided into 2 phases: Phase I flowering and Phase II flowering.

As shown in the graph, flowering twice in one vegetation period was noted only for two yucca species: *Y. aloifolia* and *Y. gloriosa*; second flowering was not recorded for the remaining species.

In general, it should be noted that yucca flowering occurs after the cessation of active vegetative bud or rosette growth cone activity. Some yucca specimens begin flowering directly in early spring instead of vegetating. Such early-flowering individuals, after finishing flowering, continue growing, and after passing through the complete phase of vegetative development, manage to flower a second time.

Thus, we can conclude that yuccas do not have clearly expressed periods of generative and vegetative phenophase progression in one vegetation period, and this changes according to the level and peculiarities of the plant's own biological development.

Phenology of Yucca Flowering (2020)

Phenology of Yucca Flowering (2021)

It should be noted that in our conditions, only one yucca species, *Y. aloifolia*, develops seeds that are capable of germination. The remaining species flower but do not produce seeds.

Yucca seeds are black in color. Their average length is up to 5.5 mm. The width is 6-7 mm. The average thickness of the seed is 2.9-3.1 mm.

Yucca seeds are slightly wrinkled and are not uniform in shape. Flat, round ones are found, and some have compressed lateral forms. These seeds also differ from each other in size. *Yucca* seeds of different sizes are characterized by different germination abilities. This heterogeneity affects the seed germination and sprouting indicators.

Yucca reproduces both vegetatively and generatively. From vegetative propagation methods, the following were selected: 1. Stem was cut at the base and then divided into 4 segments; 2. Middle part of the stem 20 cm in height; 3. Young one-year rosette; 4. Multi-year stem rosette with reduced leaves.

Percentage Indicators of Yucca Vegetative Propagation

As shown in the graph, yuccas have quite high indicators of vegetative propagation. Among yucca vegetative propagation methods, propagation by stem base segments showed the highest rooting rate. With this method of propagation, rooting reached 88%.

In our conditions, practitioners give preference to vegetative propagation for yucca reproduction. Such a method requires less expense, and the planting material is also of high quality.

Yucca is very resistant to diseases. We did not record a single case of yucca disease. No damage by pests is observed on this plant either. Moreover, some yucca specimens do not get sick even when surrounded by plants abundantly affected by pests. A pest was observed only on the narrow-leaved form of yucca. This form is damaged by field rodents. Damage was observed at the root neck. Damage to the medulla was also observed on thread yucca. This damage is systematic in late autumn and winter periods.

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